

City Branding of Sialkot: City Branding Model in order to Promote City Competitiveness

Author Details:

Dr. Jamil Ahmed Chaudhary-Associate Professor, University of Sialkot

Abstract:

The key objective of the research is to highlight the important factors which impact the branding of Sialkot city Punjab, Pakistan. Previously researchers mentioned that Cities are faced with increased competition to attract and retain residents. Due to globalization, residents now have a choice where they want to live, work and stay. Cities must therefore investigate how the use of branding strategies can increase their competitive advantage. Residents, like consumers, have needs and wants and therefore it is important that cities understand the role that branding and marketing can play to position themselves as a place where residents want to live. In the academic field, several international researchers have published articles on place/city marketing and also place/city branding, but within the Pakistan context there is limited research available on these topics. Almost 195 Questionnaires have received from different areas of Sialkot. Tool of the analysis is SPSS. The finding of this study is to develop Sialkot city branding framework within a Pakistan context. To achieve the primary objective, secondary objectives were established to measure the level of experience and importance of the city branding factors. From the results, importance–performance matrixes were developed. This study also aims to confirm and expand the existing marketing theory in terms of city branding within a Pakistan context. For that purpose, researcher will use questionnaire and conduct structured focus group from local citizen of Sialkot city

Keywords: City Branding, Sialkot

Introduction:

Branding has emerged as an important strategy in the public sector, particularly at the city level. Intercity competition has intensified in today's globalization with highly mobile capital, and local governments have become increasingly entrepreneurial. In their quest to attract new investment, tourists, and residents, local governments are turning to city branding to increase their cities' share of attention and reputation in the global marketplace (Anholt, 2015). The marketing and branding of cities have become important parts of urban governance. In the worldwide competition for tourists, inhabitants and investments, cities apply place branding to develop an attractive image and positive reputation. City marketing, meanwhile, is used widely to influence place-making elements such as a place's representations and policies. Almost all major cities now apply these strategies to improve their image. In general, city marketing can be understood as the "coordinated use of marketing tools supported by a shared customer-oriented philosophy, for creating, communicating, delivering, and exchanging urban offerings that have value for the city's customers and the city's community at large" (Braun, 2008, p. 43). Sialkot, the export city of Pakistan is earning \$900 million per annum by exports. The major exports are the sports goods, surgical instruments, leather products, martial art instruments, musical instruments and sportswear. The study of place branding has burgeoned in the past decades, and a consensus has emerged that in some ways, cities can be marketed and branded like products and/or corporations (Papadopoulos, 2004). Municipal governments select suitable city brands to express their current and potential strengths and advantages to improve the attractiveness of urban areas. In the product brand field, brand choices are studied from a variety of perspectives, such as brand credibility (Erdem & Swait, 2014), decision-making under uncertainty (Erdem & Keane, 2016) and advertising exposure (Tellis, 2015). City brand choices, however, take place in a more complex setting since decisions made by municipal governments are affected by various stakeholders, public and private. Most studies rely on single case studies rather than comparative or multiple case studies, and qualitative rather than quantitative methods (Lucarelli & Olof, 2016). This methodological preference provides rich empirical details on the process and underlying factors in city branding practices. Due to their complex background, cases vary regarding their political, economic and geographical contexts. While the city branding literature first emerged in the West, its practice has expanded globally. Asian global cities, which have successfully caught up with their peers in economic terms, are now competitively applying city branding to boost their symbolic images as advanced global cities. Moreover, in Asia mostly countries are doing city branding but its not a focused phenomenon in Pakistan. There is lot of research gap regarding city branding specially the city which have recognized worldwide due to their import goods and business (Ayesha & Khan 2014). As we know Sialkot has international fame for its exports of sports goods, surgical instruments, leather products, martial art instruments, musical instruments and sportswear. Sports

goods, surgical and musical instruments industries are more than a century old. The city is export-oriented hub and a nucleus of cottage industry. Almost all the manufacturing in these industries is exported to mainly USA and Europe under the band names of Nike, Adidas, Puma, Green Hill and a variety of other brands of surgical instruments, leather goods, leather wears, sports goods and sports wears. There are more than ten thousand registered firms working in the city. So city branding of Sialkot should be first preference of political bodies not in the Pakistan but for all over all the world.

Literature Review

Anttiroiko (2015), has devised a research entitled “City Branding as a Response to Global Intercity Competition” and believes that globalization is dramatically changing the context of urban communities and the foundations of urban development policy. In his view, under such circumstances, the main goal of cities is a competitive increase in which the position and attractiveness of a city plays an important role; as a result of city attractive-based development strategies have targeted the effective absorption of foreign resources from currents of this global space. Hence, he analyzes that today emphasis is placed on urban marketing and urban coordination, which is used as “City Branding” and aims to attract services or value added as well as attract high-tech companies. In this regard, this research suggests the hypothesis of urban attractiveness and believes that inter-city competition is basically about the ability of the city to attract the greatest possible value from global flows to promote urban development and branding can be a way to increase this charm. Finally, the author argues that the result of such an interurban competition determines the performance and position of cities in the division of global labor, the international hierarchy, and ultimately the ability of cities to increase prosperity and economic growth in urban societies. Purwanti & Genoveva (2017), in their study entitled “An Evaluation of City Branding to Reinforce the City Competitiveness”, argue that cities are real contributors to the country’s economic development; because they responsible the largest national income activities. Due to this fact, a competitive city will be a destination for mobile capital, modern producers, talent, technology, tourism, events and citizens with high incomes. They are trying to discover the principles and identity of branding through interviewing experts by relying on Kotler’s marketing theory and PEST analysis tools. The results of this research show that city branding is one of the most important means of urban marketing which can be called as a city's visage. In addition, the proper implementation of city branding strategies can help to attract the target market, satisfy the interests of urban stakeholders, and increase the competitiveness of city competitiveness in different aspects. Finally, the study aims at increase the role of brand in the promotion of urban competitiveness, providing the following offers: - Understanding of urban amenities and their use in city branding strategies in order to create meaning, philosophy and urban perspective; -Promoting the city advertising strategies to increase foreigners’ awareness of City Branding; - Ensuring a good partnership with all the city’s shareholders to create a strong brand of the city and paying attention to the strategy of integrated marketing communications. The study of city branding has proliferated in the earlier times, and unanimity has arisen that in some ways, places can be promoted and branded like products and/or organizations (Aaker & Papadopoulos, 2016). Local governments select appropriate city trademarks to express their existing and probable assets and pluses to expand the desirability of main city areas. In the product brand arena, brand ranges are considered from a multiple of viewpoints, such as brand reliability (Erdem & Swait, 2014), decision-making under indecision (Erdem & Keane, 2016) and advertising coverage (Tellis, 2008). Nonetheless, city brand choices occur in a very intricate situation because choices made by local governments are influenced by numerous stakeholders, public as well as private. While these studies have not been conducted as systematically as that of products; however, quite a few focuses on the development and key issues of city branding. Majority of the articles and studies depend on sole case studies rather than reasonable amount, and qualitative rather than empirical approaches (Lucarelli & Olof Berg, 2011). There has been a growth in the number of cities in China that are using sustainable city brands contrary to the background of urban revolution. This revolution is contained in the modification of economic layout, as a move is occurring from primary to secondary and from secondary to tertiary industrial sectors (Rozelle, & Uchida, 2008). Public governments not only strive for equilibrium among the present societal, economical and geographical structures of their cities’ but keep track of

their urban revolution as well, as presented in the self-images. Anttiroiko (2014) draws explicit attention towards the effect of the local economic growth procedures and ranking of the city on the choices of city branding in post-industrial metropolises. De Jong et al. (2018) are of the opinion that political situations and economic phase depict the choices of city branding; it also assists in its prediction and proposing a pathway method. Though, many cities are on their projected pathways but there are exceptions where some cities merely brand for green washing and follow unanticipated pathways (Han et al., 2018). This literature indicates the fundamental hypothesis of this paper: urban transformation factors influence the choices of city branding; mentioned below. Cities geographically amalgamate into large commonalities as they develop connections with each other (Halbert, 2008).

Theoretical Framework:

Theoretical Framework:

Research Philosophy

Research philosophy is the parameters on which researchers examine about the expansion of knowledge. The positivism method deals with numerical data collection approach for judging human behaviors. interpretivism deals with the realities or facts of social event (Hussey & Hussey, 1997). So, our research is positivism.

Research Design

The research particularly for this research study will be based on the hypothetical deductive approach. This approach begins from extensive literature review, conceptual modeling, developing hypothesis and generating authentic results from the help of the study (Sekaran, 2006)

Nature of Study:

The researchers will indicate “Explanatory” nature of such study. Previous studies have been taken as a base of this hypothetical. Primary data is gathered from Structured Questionnaire. Secondary data is taken from digital library, previous research and internet

Population and Sampling:

Population will be people of all area of Sialkot Population will be divide into different strata’s and purposive and random sampling technique will be adopted for data collection.

RESULTS & ANALYSIS

Demographical Statistics

Respondents were asked about certain demographics i.e. gender, qualification, age, (see Table Majority of the respondents were male (i.e. N = 166, 85.1 %), while 14.9 % were female.

Demographical Characteristics of Respondents

Demographics (n=195)		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	166	85.1
	Female	29	14.9
Age	18-26 Years	22	11.3
	27-35 Years	78	40.0
	36-47 Years	75	38.5
	48-66 Years	20	10.3
Qualification	Primary	58	29.7
	High	15	7.7
	Graduate	56	28.7
	Masters	66	33.8

Data Normality Assessment

The prior assumptions of running structural equation model and other confirmatory factor includes that data should be normally distributed. Several tests can be run for checking the normality of the data. However, commonly used test for data normality assessment researchers usually go for Kurtosis and Skewness. Descriptive analysis employed to know the results of Kurtosis and Skewness for all variables. There are two assumptions regarding values for Kurtosis and Skewness. However, the values for Skewness should be in between +3 to -3 and values for Kurtosis should be less than +10 to -10. Results reveal that all variables are normally distributed. Table values for Kurtosis and Skewness are in between -1 to +1. However, negative values resulted for Skewness and Kurtosis. Tables for Skewness and Kurtosis are given in Appendix Secondly, P-plots are used to check the multivariate outliers and flow of the data. Q-Q plot results reveal that data followed the same path in all variables. In P-Plots standard residuals for all variables are examined. For this particular study, the P-Plots show that standard residuals are normal for all variables

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
CB	195	4.0103	.96725	-2.030	.174	2.834	.346
LSI	195	3.6015	.93191	-1.356	.174	.368	.346
VS	195	3.7872	1.12015	-1.369	.174	.247	.346
I	195	3.8756	1.07675	-1.439	.174	.580	.346
E	195	4.0474	1.03514	-1.752	.174	1.761	.346
S	195	3.6000	.86803	-1.462	.174	1.647	.346

LSS	195	2.1833	1.08471	1.483	.174	.615	.346
EM	195	3.4214	1.29704	-.621	.174	-1.380	.346
B	195	3.3041	1.32060	-.432	.174	-1.658	.346
SMC	195	3.7128	1.14433	-1.139	.174	-.347	.346
C	195	3.8756	.92481	-2.007	.174	2.906	.346
H	195	1.8487	1.00031	2.130	.174	3.069	.346
Valid N (listwise)	195						

OUTLIERS AND DIAGNOSIS

The descriptive statistics checked the responses or multivariate outliers before the data analysis of the survey respondents. Outliers are those cases or observations in the data with exceptional character as these are exclusively different from the rest observations and may be retaining with a high or low value of a particular variable. Outliers are perhaps beneficial or sometimes stand problematic. The beneficial outliers are those values in the variables that are not discovered in the normal observation analysis whereas the problematic outliers are not the actual representative of the population and hence it could affect the statistical findings and results (Hair et. al., 2010). Outlier's detection is done by adopting the technique of Z scoring method. The detected outliers were checked through standardization as well taking the z scores of those and transformed them in the original distribution where mean becomes zero and standard deviation becomes one.

MISSING VALUE ANALYSIS

The missing values of the data were analyzed on SPSS as its mandatory for the analysis of data. There are two main reasons of missing in data i.e., omission of data entered from the original questionnaire/ instrument and involuntary missing of response by the sampling subject/ respondent. The missing value analysis represents the degree of completeness of data (Brown, 1994). No missing value in the data is seen and henceforth in the 305 questionnaires no respondent answer was missing and it shows that data is normal.

FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION

The frequency distribution throws light on the data collected from the respondents about the items taken into consideration for the measurement of variables under study. The frequency distribution demonstrates the opinion/trend of responses of the respondent's degree of agreement and non-agreement towards the contents of research.

RELIABILITY OF VARIABLES

The data collected from the survey respondents through the instrument/questionnaire must be reliable in aspects of its contents and constructs. Patten (2004) claimed that an instrument is considerably legitimate and genuine if its reliability is attained. Legitimacy of the instrument provides facilitation to the researcher and experts in lieu of research design and ultimately justifies for what they are looking into (Wallen and Fraenkel, 2001). Reliability of instrument is core to make out the reliable outcomes each time. Wallen and Fraenkel (2001) highlighted that the reliability aspect of instrument is decided on the basis of result/outcome it provides on random and simultaneous testing. Patten (2004) also recommends that great focus would be applied to securing legitimate information and reliable outcomes. Miles and Huberman (1994) demonstrated that the reliability of the instrument implies to the operationalization of a research study which encompasses the repeated activity of data collection providing the same results provoking with almost same degree of responsiveness from the sampling subjects. Reliability of the instrument is measured by the most commonly used test of cronbatch alpha (Ayes, 1998). Bair *et. al* (1995) claimed that the range of acceptability index of cronbatch alpha is .6 to .9. Pallant (2000) put same annotations on the goodness index of cronbatch alpha as the coefficient value of alpha ranges from 0 to 1. Henceforth, Vellis(1991) claimed that the coefficient of cronbach alpha is associated with

the internal excellence of the contents of the variable. Sekaran (2000) categorized the cronbach alpha coefficient excellence degrees and suggested that the coefficient value of reliability less than 0.6 are inadequate, values within the range of 0.7 are taken on satisfactory level where as the values till 0.8 are good and 0.9 are taken as excellent. This categorization shows that the values near to 1 are closer to the excellence. This range among the internal excellence of factors facilitates the credibility as well as provides the assistance in ascertaining the relationship among the factors/contents of the variables.

Reliability Analyses

Name of the Factor	Cronbach’s Alpha	No of Items
Lifestyle & Social Interaction	0.785	7
Vision & Strategy	0.916	4
Image	0.919	4
Education	0.924	4
Safety	0.732	4
Leisure & Sialkotscape	0.887	4
Employement	0.932	4
Business	0.927	4
City Branding	0.936	5
Shopping & Medical Care	0.916	4
Culture	0.914	4
Housing	0.950	6
Total	0.739	54

REGRESSION ANALYSIS

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.989 ^a	.979	.978	.14769

a. Predictors: (Constant), H, LSI, LSS, C, SMC, E, B, I

REGRESSION ANALYSIS

The adjusted R square value explains the change in dependent variable due to independent variables. The adjusted R Square value is .978 which means that 98% change can be occurred in dependent variables due to change in independent variables.

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.682	.395		6.787	.000
	LSI	.529	.064	.510	8.226	.000
	VS	.446	.052	.539	8.894	.000
	I	.620	.047	.690	13.241	.000
	E	.742	.041	.794	18.138	.000
	S	.958	.041	.860	23.294	.000
	LSS	-.609	.047	-.683	-12.973	.000
	EM	.184	.052	.247	3.540	.001
	B	.114	.052	.155	2.184	.030
	SMC	.465	.051	.550	9.151	.000
	C	.954	.031	.912	30.926	.000
	H	-.897	.026	-.928	-34.472	.000

a. Dependent Variable: CB

The beta value for lifestyle and social interaction is 0.510, which shows a strong positive significant impact on city branding, whereas the (Sig. < .05). The beta value for vision & strategy is 0.539, which shows a strong positive significant impact on city branding, whereas the (Sig. < .05). The beta value for image is 0.690, which shows a positive significant impact on city branding, whereas the (Sig. < .05). The beta value for education is 0.794, which shows a strong positive significant impact on city branding, whereas the (Sig. < .05). The beta value for safety is 0.860, which shows a positive significant impact on city branding, whereas the (Sig. < .05). The beta value for leisure and Sialkot scape is -.683, which shows a negative significant impact on city branding, whereas the (Sig. < .05). The beta value for employment is .247, which shows a positive significant impact on city branding, whereas the (Sig. < .05). The beta value for business is .155, which shows a positive significant impact on city branding, whereas the (Sig. < .05). The beta value for shopping & medical care is .550, which shows a moderate positive significant impact on city branding, whereas the (Sig. < .05). The beta value for culture is .912, which shows a strong positive significant impact on city branding, whereas the (Sig. < .05). The beta value for housing is -.928, which shows a positive significant impact on city branding, whereas the (Sig. < .05). The probability is that they will support the tourism industry when they feel involved in the interchange or advantages from the development. Moreover, tourism can create the demand for cultural, ethnic and folk activities, creating venues, and other conveniences that might develop residents' quality of life.

Conclusion:

Sialkot is the city which known in all over the world due to sports good and leather products. So it's very important to develop a brand image of Sialkot into the world. This study is one of the early investigations of the Branding efforts of city in Pakistan. Such studies have been done on big cities like New York, Amsterdam, Austin and Las Vegas but developing countries need to work on Branding efforts to increase the number of tourists and visitors, also to get a good image of the city or region. Good branding efforts play a vibrant role in re-vamping the image of that region. This study particularly studied the role and participations of residents in branding a city keeping in view the brand associations which make an individual to speak for his/her city. Keeping in mind the hypothesis city brand managers should increase brand associations by highlighting the

important and historical building that truly represent the essence and history of the city. Historical buildings and heritage sights are very influential in branding process of a city. Food and culture festivals should be celebrated religiously to make sure citizens do not lose touch of their connection with the city. Proper branding of Sialkot and these festivals along with creation of logos, catchy phrases and slogans should be made to penetrate in the target market to create positive and strong images of the city brand. For example, at every product of Sialkot there should be a logo of Sialkot So that hold a very sacred place in the eyes of the resident because of its significance for the nation. Stakeholder involvement is considered important in the brand building process. This study demonstrates that marketing and branding campaigns can craft positive attitudes in residents toward a destination's brand and successively lead to residents that are loyal to the branding efforts of a target city. This study is for the politician and other institutes of Sialkot for enhancing the brand image into the world.

Research Implications and Recommendations for Future Research

Diving deeper into the study of essentials that lead citizens to sense support for the development of tourism is significant for hospitality and tourism stakeholders, as well as for the extended hosting community, plus native administration and commerce. Support on local level can assist in the development and growth of tourism (Gursoy & Rutherford, 2014). Keeping in mind the factors that will turn the citizens into brand advocates for the city can prove to be an effective way to promote city branding efforts and it will ensure less obstacles and more smooth campaigns, resulting in improved branding and improved relationship between all key stakeholders. For further research Brand personality can be studied to pursue the self-brand connection studies by studying human personality and its impact on Brand advocacy for the city. According to Aaker (2017) cities have personalities and they are personified as their personalities are used in branding efforts. It can be studied that whether or not Brand personalities of humans and cities have a relationship and support participatory branding.

References:

- i. Aaker, D. (1991). *Managing Brand Equity*, The Free Press, New York.
- ii. Agarwal, M. K., & Rao, V. R. (1996). *An empirical comparison of consumer-based measures of brand equity*. *Marketing letters*, 7(3), 237-247.
- iii. Ashworth, G.J. and Voogd, H. (1990), *Selling the City: Marketing Approaches in Public Sector Urban Planning*, Belhaven, London.
- iv. Bauer, H. H., Heinrich, D., & Martin, I. (2007, December). *How to create high emotional consumer-brand relationships? The causalities of brand passion*. In 2007 Australian & New Zealand Marketing Academy Conference Proceedings (pp. 2189-2198).
- v. Balmer, J. M. (2011). *Corporate heritage identities, corporate heritage brands and the multiple heritage identities of the British Monarchy*. *European Journal of Marketing*, 45(9/10), 1380-1398.
- vi. Baloglu, S., Henthorne, T. L., & Sahin, S. (2014). *Destination image and brand personality of Jamaica: A model of tourist behavior*. *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing*, 31(8), 1057-1070.
- vii. Bearden, W. O., & Etzel, M. J. (1982). *Reference group influence on product and brand purchase decisions*. *Journal of consumer research*, 9(2), 183-194.
- viii. Bettencourt, L. (1997). *Customer Voluntary Performance: Customer as Partners in Service Delivery*. *Journal of Retailing*, 73, 383-406.
- ix. Belk, R. W. (1988). *Possessions and the extended self*. *Journal of consumer research*, 15(2), 139-168.
- x. Bizman, A., Yinon, Y., (2002). *Engaging in distancing tactics among sport fans: effects on self-esteem and emotional responses*. *The Journal of Social Psychology* 142 (3), 381-392
- xi. Brewer, M. B. (1991). *The social self: On being the same and different at the same time*. *Personality and social psychology bulletin*, 17(5), 475-482.
- xii. Carpenter, G. S., Glazer, R., & Nakamoto, K. (1994). *Meaningful brands from meaningless differentiation: The dependence on irrelevant attributes*. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 339-350.

- xiii. Chaplin, L. N., & John, D. R. (2005). *The development of self-brand connections in children and adolescents*. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 32(1), 119-129.
- xiv. Chaudhuri, Arjun and Morris B. Holbrook (2001), *.The Chain of Effects from Brand Trust and Brand Affect to Brand Performance: The Role of Brand Loyalty*,. *Journal of Marketing*, 65 (April), 81-93.
- xv. Cheng, S. Y., White, T. B., & Chaplin, L. N. (2012). *The effects of self-brand connections on responses to brand failure: A new look at the consumer–brand relationship*. *Journal of Consumer Psychology*, 22(2), 280-288.
- xvi. Crang, M. (1998). *Cultural geography*. Psychology Press.
- xvii. Cooper, H., Schembri, S. and Miller, D. (2010), “Brand selfidentity narratives in the James Bond movies”, *Psychology & Marketing*, Vol. 27 No. 6, pp. 557-67.
- xviii. Dawar, Niraj and Madan M. Pillutla (2000), *.Impact of Product-Harm Crises on Brand Equity: The Moderating Role of Consumer Expectations*,. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 37 (May), 215-226.
- xix. Dhar, R., & Sherman, S. J. (1996). *The effect of common and unique features in consumer choice*. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 23(3), 193-203. 53
- xx. Dolich, I. J. (1969). *Congruence relationships between self images and product brands*. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 80-84.
- xxi. Dodds, W.B., Monroe, K.B. and Grewal, D. (1991), “Effects of price, brand and store information on buyers’ product evaluations”, *Journal of Marketing Research*, Vol. 28 No. 3, pp. 307-19.
- xxii. Eagly, A.H., Chaiken, S., (1993). *The Psychology of Attitudes*, Harcourt Brace Jovanovich, Fort Worth.
- xxiii. Eastman, J.K., Goldsmith, R.E., Flynn, L. R., 1999. *Status consumption in consumer behaviour: scale development and validation*. *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice* 7 (3), 41-51.
- xxiv. Eisenstadt, S.N., (1968). *Prestige, participation and strata formation*. In: Jackson, J.A. (Ed.), *Social Stratification*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, pp. 62-103.
- xxv. Escalas, J. E., & Bettman, J. R. (2003). *You are what they eat: The influence of reference groups on consumers’ connections to brands*. *Journal of consumer psychology*, 13(3), 339-348.
- xxvi. Eisenstadt, S. N. (1968). *Social institutions: comparative study*. Collier-Macmillan.
- xxvii. Eshuis, J., & Edwards, A. (2013). *Branding the city: The democratic legitimacy of a new mode of governance*. *Urban Studies*, 50(5), 1066-1082.
- xxviii. Fazio, R. H., & Zanna, M. P. (1981). *Direct experience and attitude-behavior consistency*. *Advances in experimental social psychology*, 14, 161-202.
- xxix. Rainisto, S. K. (2003). *Success factors of place marketing: A study of place marketing practices in Northern Europe and the United States*. Helsinki University of Technology.
- xxx. Rossiter, J. R., & Percy, L. (1987). *Advertising and promotion management*. McGraw-Hill Book Company.
- xxxi. Rusticus, S. (2006). *Creating brand advocates*. In J. Kirby & P. Marsden (Eds.), *Connected marketing: The viral, buzz and word-of-mouth revolution* (p. 49). London, England: Elsevier.
- xxxii. Runyan, R. and Huddleson, P. (2006), “Getting customers downtown: the role of branding in achieving success for central business districts”, *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, Vol. 15 No. 1, pp. 48-61.
- xxxiii. Sahin, S., & Baloglu, S. (2014). *City Branding: Investigating a Brand Advocacy Model for Distinct Segments*. *Journal of Hospitality Marketing & Management*, 23(3), 239-265.
- xxxiv. Schultz, M. (2005). *Corporate branding: Purpose/people/process: Towards the second wave of corporate branding*. Copenhagen Business School Press DK.
- xxxv. Schlenker, B. R. (1980). *Impression management*. Brooks/Cole Publishing Company.
- xxxvi. Shaw, S. J., & Macleod, N. E. (2000). *Creativity and conflict: cultural tourism in London’s city fringe*. *Tourism Culture & Communication*, 2(3), 165-175.
- xxxvii. Scott, J. (2011). *Social network analysis: developments, advances, and prospects*. *Social network analysis and mining*, 1(1), 21-26.

- xxxviii. Stets, J. E., & Burke, P. J. (2000). *Identity theory and social identity theory*. *Social psychology quarterly*, 224-237.
- xxxix. Tajfel, H. (1974). *Social identity and intergroup behaviour*. *Information (International Social Science Council)*, 13(2), 65-93.